

D1.1. ANALYSIS AND PORTFOLIO OF PROFESSIONAL
SKILLS AND COMPETENCES FOR OPEN SCIENCE

December 2024

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
OS	Open Science
KV	Knowledge Valorisation
R&I	Research and Innovation
RM	Research Manager
WP	Work Package

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Executive summary

Introduction

This deliverable aims to establish a comprehensive framework for the skills and competencies required by researchers and Research Managers (RM) to accelerate research impact through knowledge valorisation using open science (OS) practices involving 4H actors. By identifying these essential skills, the deliverable will serve as a foundation for developing targeted training programs to up-skill researchers. The skills were identified through a co-creation process involving actors from the quadruple helix (QH), who helped to detect the necessary skills for open science profiles and provided insights into current skills gaps. This approach will facilitate the shift from traditional knowledge transfer to the valorisation of knowledge co-generated by diverse actors within complex research and innovation ecosystems, based on OS principles.

Methodology

Initially, the consortium established clear definitions for key concepts (researchers, RM, OS, knowledge valorisation). Following this, regional networks—including representatives from civil society, public administration, industry, and academia— were identified by the universities to get involved in the process of the validation of key researchers' and RM skills related to OS. Utilizing the ResearchComp and RMComp, the consortium pre-selected skills pertinent to OS for validation through a comprehensive survey. It was meticulously designed to accommodate varying levels of familiarity with OS and was distributed across university networks. Data analysis revealed researchers' and RM key skills for OS, those most effectively acquired, and areas needing improvement, particularly in systemic vision, collaboration, and impact.

Researchers' skills

Beyond the ResearchComp skills pre-selected by the consortium and validated by more than 95% of the survey participants—strategic, systemic, abstract, and critical thinking—stakeholders identified additional crucial competencies: creativity, decision-making, empathy, emotional intelligence, and ecological thinking. Empathy and emotional skills align with the LifeComp framework, while ecological thinking resonates with the GreenComp framework. Computational thinking aligns with DigComp competencies. Skills related to collaboration and impact, such as creativity, interdisciplinary research, and communication, were also emphasized for fostering a systemic vision. Analytical and critical thinking were highlighted as key strengths among researchers. However, strategic and systemic thinking were identified as areas needing improvement, reflecting a shift towards fostering leadership and adaptability in research careers to meet the evolving demands of innovation ecosystems.

The survey revealed that over 95% of participants identified essential collaboration skills, including to interact professionally, conduct interdisciplinary research, work in teams, promote inclusion and diversity, and to develop networks. These skills are valued by both academic and non-academic stakeholders for effective communication and cooperation. However, there is a discrepancy in the importance placed on resource mobilization, negotiation, and creativity, with non-academic stakeholders emphasizing these skills more due to their relevance in leadership and project funding. For collaboration Stakeholders' reflections highlighted several additional skills such as: delegation, empathy, and a request to change the wording from "negotiate" to "generate consensus." Additionally, skills that align closely with the LifeComp framework, such as empathy and flexibility, were identified as essential. The capacity for multi-stakeholder collaboration and strong communication skills were also emphasized, underscoring the importance of inclusivity and the ability to navigate complex social dynamics. Researchers' strengths in collaboration include developing networks, professional interaction, and teamwork. On the contrary, interdisciplinary research and promoting inclusion and diversity were highlighted as areas needing improvement. This highlights the necessity for researchers to develop practical, cross-sectoral skills to engage effectively with the broader innovation ecosystem.

A consensus was reached on essential impact-related skills: promoting knowledge transfer, applying research ethics and integrity, increasing science's impact on policy and society, managing research data, promoting open innovation, communicating to the public, and promoting open access publications. Teaching in academic or vocational contexts was also deemed crucial for maximizing impact. External stakeholders highlighted the importance of promoting citizen science and managing intellectual property. Additional key skills for impact include continuous learning, adaptive evaluation, social analysis, strategic sustainability, futures literacy, and political agency. Researchers' strengths include disseminating research findings, managing research data, and teaching. However, areas for improvement include enhancing societal engagement, increasing research influence on policy and society, and promoting citizen science. This highlights the need for researchers to develop skills that extend beyond academia to effectively engage with the broader community and drive innovation.

Research Managers' skills

The research highlights key skills for research managers (RMs) relevant to systemic vision, with over 95% of survey participants agreeing on cultural sensibility, strategic planning, problem solving, critical thinking, and decision making. Problem solving is valued by all non-academic actors and RMs, while critical thinking is important to nearly all participants. Additional competencies suggested include systems thinking and empathy. Non-academic actors also recommend research financial management, managing learning, wellbeing, and openness to feedback. Researchers propose administrative thinking, project management, ethical aspects, social competencies, and co-creation. RMs suggest systemic, analytical, and abstract thinking, along with communication skills. Strengths identified include decision making, problem solving, and strategic planning, while areas for improvement are cultural sensibility and strategic planning.

RMs need various skills for effective collaboration. Over 95% of survey participants agree on the importance of building and maintaining relationships with funders and stakeholders, building trust in partnerships, diplomacy, negotiation, mediation, people management, team performance, professional flexibility, team building, handling difficult conversations, managing equality, diversity, and inclusion, and coaching. Non-academic actors also value business and commercial liaison management, unlike some researchers and RMs. Additional competencies suggested include subject matter expertise, research project oversight, and empathy. Non-academic actors also recommend budgetary and financial management, assertiveness, impartiality, patience, and training on transformative innovation. Researchers suggest skills in research project oversight, ethics, and integrity, while RMs emphasize establishing research project plans. Strengths in collaboration include relationship building, professional flexibility, and trust-building. Areas for improvement are managing equality, diversity, and inclusion.

Survey participants identified several additional skills relevant to impact for research managers (RMs). Non-academic actors highlighted skills aligned with RMComp, such as media activities, pre-award and post-award processes, and research ethics and integrity. They also emphasized continuous learning (aligned with LifeComp) and digitalization (aligned with DigComp). Researchers suggested skills in social and people caring, welfare, ethics (aligned with RMComp and LifeComp), and sustainability issues (aligned with GreenComp). RMs themselves recommended capacity building and training skills, aligned with RMComp and LifeComp.

Strengths in impact-related skills include academic community relationship collaboration and monitoring and evaluation frameworks. However, social media engagement was identified as an area needing improvement. This summary underscores the importance of diverse competencies for RMs to effectively manage and enhance the impact of their research activities.

Conclusions

Quadruple Helix stakeholders identified additional skills for researchers and research managers (RMs) that align with GreenComp, LifeComp, and DigComp frameworks. These skills emphasize interdisciplinarity, sustainability, and digital literacy, highlighting the need for adaptability in addressing emerging challenges. By incorporating these competencies, the 4H framework provides a comprehensive understanding of the

skills required for success in complex, interdisciplinary, and innovation-driven environments, ensuring researchers and RMs can contribute meaningfully to global and societal challenges.

LifeComp skills such as flexibility, empathy, and well-being management are identified as essential for researchers to thrive in dynamic, collaborative settings. Moreover, a gap in systemic and strategic vision was identified, which could limit researchers' ability to grasp the broader implications of their work, reducing their potential to influence policy and address societal and environmental challenges, and leading to missed opportunities for knowledge valorisation.

The diverse skills identified for RMs underscore their crucial role in research and innovation ecosystems. This highlights the need to professionalize and recognize their expertise. RMs are key facilitators, fostering community engagement, building trust, and managing difficult conversations. Their ability to create connections, streamline processes, and foster synergies across stakeholders is essential for advancing open science practices and knowledge valorisation. This highlights their essential role in advancing open science practices and knowledge valorisation.

A comparative analysis highlights complementary skills between researchers and RMs, emphasizing their synergies and interdependencies within research and innovation ecosystems. This underscores the critical interplay between the two roles and suggests targeted institutional initiatives to optimize their combined impact and enhance the overall effectiveness of the research and innovation process.

1. Introduction

The objectives of Work Package (WP) 1 and the associated tasks are designed to accomplish the overall goal of the WP. An overview of the content of the deliverable is provided in the following subsections:

1.1 Objectives of the WP and tasks

The overall objective of WP1 is to equip universities and researchers with the tools and skills needed to move from the traditional concept of knowledge transfer to a valorisation of knowledge co-generated by different actors in complex R&I ecosystems model based on Open Science (OS) principles. To do so WP1 will implement the following objectives:

- Provide a comprehensive overview of current skills and competences for professionals (both researchers and research managers (RMs) to work with an Open Science model for knowledge valorisation (KV)
- Pilot different research training programmes to implement and accelerate KV practices at different Universities.
- Set the foundations of a multidisciplinary network of professionals working with open science-based knowledge valorisation.
- Develop an Action Plan for embedding and accelerating KV practices within the Consortium and translate It into guidelines for its further implementation beyond the project life.

The tasks of WP1 are: 1) to create a definition of open science professional profile for managers and researchers; 2) to co-create and implement a researchers' training with content on open science, entrepreneurship, social innovation, innovation management and stakeholder engagement; 3) to exchange good practices among universities to equip researchers and RMs to act as enablers and facilitators in the implementation of open Science-based Knowledge Valorisation Best Practices within their ecosystems; 4) to establish a network of OS professionals and 5) to develop an Action Plan for embedding and accelerating KV good practices at universities.

1.2 Content of the Deliverable

Deliverable 1.1. will focus on the methodology followed to identify open science skills for researchers and RMs and results obtained. The skills will be identified by means of a co-creation process where actors from the quadruple helix (QH) will contribute to detect the needed skills for open science profiles for researchers and RMs as well as their perception on the current skills and gaps. This deliverable contains the details of the co-creation sessions devoted to identifying the skills within the consortium members as well as the content, the results and analysis of the survey that was extended to the QH actors to agree on the definition of the professional skills and competences that both researchers and RM should need to implement an open science-based innovation management.

2. Aim

The purpose of this deliverable is to establish a comprehensive framework for the skills and competencies required by researchers and RMs to effectively transition to an open science and innovation management approach. By identifying these essential professional skills, the deliverable will serve as a foundation for developing targeted training programs (Task 1.2 for researchers and Task 1.3 for research and innovation managers, along with Deliverables 1.2 and 1.3).

This program will empower researchers and RMs to enhance their capabilities in fostering innovation, promoting collaboration with societal stakeholders, and ensuring that research outputs are effectively utilized and valorised. Ultimately, this will support the broader goals of advancing open science, maximizing the societal impact of research, and deepening competencies in open science and innovation management.

3. Theoretical Background

The theoretical foundation of this deliverable, aimed at defining the skills and competencies necessary for researchers and RMs to transition to an open science and innovation management approach, is grounded in several key frameworks and concepts. These frameworks and concepts underpin the rationale for upskilling and training within the evolving research and innovation landscape, forming the basis for the chosen methodological approach:

Open Science framework

The UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science¹ provides an international framework for open science policy and practice that recognizes disciplinary and regional differences in OS perspectives. It considers academic freedom, gender-transformative approaches and the specific challenges of scientists and other OS actors in different countries, particularly in developing nations. It also contributes to reducing the digital, technological and knowledge divides existing between and within countries. UNESCO Open Science definition: involves opening the processes of creating, evaluating, sharing, exploring and storing scientific knowledge, practices and perspectives. More in detail, OS is defined as an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices, aiming to: (i) make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, (ii) increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and (iii) open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community. All scientific disciplines of scholarly practices, including basic and applied sciences, natural and social sciences and the humanities are included.

Open science builds on four key pillars: open scientific knowledge, open science infrastructures, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems.

Skills competence frameworks for Researchers

ResearchComp: ResearchComp² is the first competence framework for researchers at EU level, developed on the basis of the most recent analysis of the transversal skills that researchers need for successful and interoperable careers in all sectors of the society (academia, industry, business, public administration, NGOs etc.). ResearchComp is aligned with the European Skills, Competences, and Occupations classification (ESCO)³, as it has been developed based on the taxonomy of transversal skills for researchers that was included in the 2022 version of the classification.

As illustrated in Figure 1, ResearchComp has 7 competence areas (cognitive abilities, doing research, managing research, managing research tools, making an impact, working with others, self-management) and 38 competences that gave rise to 389 learning outcomes along 4 proficiency levels (foundational, intermediate, advanced, expert).

¹ <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949>

² https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/7da29338-37bf-4d51-b5eb-a1571b84c7ad_en?filename=ec_rtd_research-competence-presentation.pdf

³ https://esco.ec.europa.eu/en/classification/skill_main

Figure 1: Illustration of ResearchComp

A number of other sector-specific EU competence frameworks were developed by the Commission and the Joint Research Centre before ResearchComp (e.g. the Digital Competence Framework for Citizens (DigComp), the European entrepreneurship competence framework (EntreComp)⁴, (GreenComp)⁵ for sustainability competences and the European Framework for the personal, social and learning to learn key competence (LifeComp)⁶. During the development of ResearchComp, the Commission has ensured that competences which are similar to those contained in other EU competence frameworks are aligned, for clarity and coherence.

Skills competence frameworks for research managers

The CARDEA RM Competency Framework: Although several competence frameworks for RMs that reflect the diverse nature of the role and its responsibilities are available, The CARDEA RM Competency Framework was born from the need for a European Research manager competence framework that acknowledges the diverse tasks and duties undertaken by RMs.

Similarly to ResearchComp, The CARDEA Research Manager Competency Framework⁷ has 8 competence areas (Cognitive Abilities/Transversal Skills, Technical Proficiency, Subject Matter Expertise, Research Project Oversight, Community Engagement, Line Management and Talent Development, Communication and Relationship Management) with a total of 42 competences and 672 learning outcomes along 4

⁴ <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC101581>

⁵ <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC128040>

⁶ <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC120911>

⁷ <https://www.ucc.ie/en/media/support/hrresearch/hrresearchtraining/RMCompMay2024.pdf>

proficiency levels (foundational, intermediate, advanced, expert) associated. Figure 2 depicts the competences encompassed within each core competency.

Figure 2: CARDEA Research Management Competences diagram.

This diagram serves as a foundational reference for RMs and stakeholders, providing a starting point to tailor their approaches according to their specific needs.

Key concepts definitions:

EC definition of Knowledge Valorisation: Knowledge valorisation is defined as "the process of creating social and economic value from knowledge by linking different areas and sectors and by transforming data, know-how and research results into sustainable products, services, solutions and knowledge-based policies that benefit society"⁸.

EC definition of Researchers: Researchers "conduct research, foster innovation, contribute to solutions to societal challenges and provide policymakers with evidence for informed decision-making processes"⁹

CARDEA's provisional definition of Research manager: A research manager is someone who "enable[s] the performance of research in all its applications. Research Managers hold specialised or generalist roles within the research ecosystem"¹⁰

⁸ <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reco/2022/2415/oj>

⁹ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:C_202301640

¹⁰

<https://www.ucc.ie/en/media/support/hrresearch/CARDEAMatrixFrameworkforResearchManagerCareerNovember2023VersionDraft.pdf>

4 Methodology and Results

To create a skills/competence framework for researchers and RMs on open science, the following methodology steps were undertaken:

1. Agreement on key terms: The first step involved reaching a consensus at the consortium level on the definitions of key terms such as “open science” and “research managers.” This was crucial since these terms can have different meanings and focuses on various contexts.
2. Pre-selection of skills: A preliminary selection of skills relevant to researchers and RMs was made at the consortium level. This step aimed to ensure that the subsequent survey would be accurate and comprehensive.
3. Identification of stakeholder typologies: The next step was to identify the different types of stakeholders to be included in the survey, such as local, regional and national government institutions, start-ups, SMEs and large enterprises, NGOs and associations. This was important to tailor the language and level of detail of the survey concepts to the specific needs and understanding of each stakeholder group.
4. Survey development: Based on the pre-selected skills and identified stakeholder typologies, a detailed survey was developed. This survey was designed to gather input on the necessary competencies for knowledge valorisation transition through open science practices involving a broad range of stakeholders.
5. Survey distribution in the networks: The partner Universities launched the survey in June, and had several iterations with the stakeholders from their networks to gather responses to the survey.
6. Analysis of survey responses and Competence Framework development: The survey responses were collected and analysed to identify common themes and specific competency requirements. This analysis helped in refining the competence framework. Using the insights gained from the survey, a comprehensive competence framework was developed. This framework included detailed descriptions of the skills and competencies required for researchers and RMs according to QH actors to effectively engage in open science.
7. Validation and refinement: The draft framework was then validated through feedback from consortium members and other stakeholders. Based on this feedback, further refinements were made to ensure the framework’s relevance and applicability.

4.1 Agreement on key terms

To establish a common understanding of essential terms like “open science” and “research managers,” the consortium was engaged in discussions to explore various definitions and contexts. This collaborative process ensured that all members had a shared understanding and that the terms were clearly defined for the framework. The outcome was a set of agreed-upon definitions that reflect the consortium’s collective perspective, providing a consistent basis for the framework’s development and application.

KALEIDOS' open science definition: KALEIDOS' relies on the UNESCO definition of open science, which encompasses various approaches, including open data and open source. However, as stated in the proposal, KALEIDOS aims to facilitate effective engagement strategies to enable open innovation and open science within ecosystems for knowledge valorisation. This involves timely, adequate, and efficient engagement with key stakeholders of the quadruple helix, which is crucial for knowledge transfer and for successful innovations to reach society.

For these reasons, KALEIDOS' consortium agreed on an operational definition, prioritizing two of the four pillars included in the UNESCO definition: open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems. Based on this and inspired by the Public Administration School of Catalonia who developed the "Competency framework for collaborative work in research and innovation"¹¹, and structured the competencies grouped in three blocks: holistic perspective, focus on transformation, and radical collaboration, three 3 key areas were suggested to be highlighted in KALEIDOS' open science definition: collaboration, impact, and a systemic or ecosystem approach.

After deliberation, the agreed operational definition is:

Open science as a collaborative (inclusive, transdisciplinary, and intersectoral) and impactful way of doing science with a systemic vision.

The consortium also agreed to group the skills and competencies related to Open Science following the three blocks previously agreed: **systemic vision, collaboration, and impact.**

Research Managers' definitions: Research, innovation and project managers play diverse and critical roles within organizations, with each position defined by its specific responsibilities. For example, **Research & Development (R&D) Managers** oversee the development and enhancement of products, services, or processes, ensuring alignment with research goals and market needs. **Innovation Managers** implement strategies to improve operational efficiency while fostering a culture of innovation, ensuring that new ideas are continuously generated and applied. **Project Managers**, on the other hand, coordinate research and innovation projects from inception to completion, managing resources, timelines, and cross-functional teams to achieve project objectives.

To establish a shared understanding of the role of research and innovation managers, the consortium agreed on a comprehensive definition aligned with the purpose of the proposal.

Research managers/innovation managers contribute to establishing vision and goals, building and implementing research plans and managing the execution of the correspondent activities. RMs/innovation managers usually act as connectors between academic and non-academic actors

4.2 Pre-selection of skills

A preliminary selection of skills relevant to both researchers and RM was conducted at the consortium level to ensure that the forthcoming survey would be accurate and comprehensive. For this pre-selection, the ResearchComp Competence framework was used for researchers, while the RMComp Competence framework proposed by the EU-funded project CARDEA guided the selection for RM. The agreed definition

¹¹

https://eapc.gencat.cat/web/.content/home/publicacions/col_leccio_eines_per_als_recursos_humans/1_2_Marc_competencial_treball_colaboratiu/Eines-12_en.pdf

of Open Science (OS) was the basis for the prioritization process, with a focus on skills related to collaboration, impact, and systemic vision.

In a face-to-face workshop the consortium was divided into two groups, with members from the same institution placed in different groups when possible. One group concentrated on identifying the key skills researchers need to effectively engage in OS practices, such as collaboration, knowledge sharing, and generating societal impact, based on predefined criteria. Simultaneously, the second group focused on determining the essential skills for RMs to support and implement OS principles within their roles (See Figure 3.). After completing their respective tasks, the groups switched to evaluate the skill requirements for the other target group. This cross-evaluation ensured a thorough and well-rounded analysis of the skills needed for both researchers and RMs.

Figure 3: Pre-selection of competences for Researchers and RM

Finally, the results from both groups were compared and integrated, leading to the consolidation of a framework of KALEIDOS OS skills tailored for both researchers and RMs, as it can be seen in Fig 4. This approach ensured a thorough understanding of the distinct, yet complementary skill sets required by each role in advancing open science practices.

Figure 4: Consolidation of the framework of KALEIDOS OS skills

4.3 Identification of stakeholder typologies

The next step in the process was to identify the different types of stakeholders for the survey and assess their awareness of Open Science (OS) practices. This was crucial for tailoring the survey's language and level of detail to the specific needs and understanding of each group. By customizing the content for stakeholders such as academic researchers, industry professionals, policymakers, and civil society, the team ensured the questions were both relevant and accessible, ultimately leading to better engagement and more accurate responses.

For this exercise, the 5 universities involved in the project were asked to complete a matrix, by identifying different stakeholders expected to include in the survey and their level of knowledge about open science and open science practices, as it can be seen in Fig 5.

Figure 5: Identification of stakeholders and the level of knowledge about open science and open science

Different universities identified different types of stakeholders with differing levels of knowledge about OS within their networks. Also, it was noticed the different level of awareness raising among different institutions and ecosystems. Academic stakeholders were expected to be more familiar with the technical language and concepts of OS compared to other groups. In response to this, the survey was designed with language appropriate to engage not only academics but also business stakeholders, government representatives, and civil society, ensuring it resonated with all participants regardless of their familiarity with Open Science. To achieve that, UAB contextualised the survey in detail, by including the definitions of Open Science, Knowledge Valorisation, Researchers and Research Managers, and introducing the ResearchComp and the RMComp.

4.4 Survey Development and Distribution

The four preceding stages were key in developing and designing a preliminary survey, which was structured in Mural format and presented to the consortium on an online workshop in March 19, 2024, for discussion. During this session, UAB facilitated the collection of feedback and proposals from the various partners, fostering collaborative input to refine the survey. Following the workshop, a final version of the survey was

consolidated, incorporating all contributions from the consortium. This final text was shared for revision and agreed upon by all members (see complete survey text in Annex I).

Figure 6: Screenshot of the Mural board used in the co-creation session aimed at defining the survey

The survey was designed to achieve two main objectives: A) defining the portfolio of skills/competencies for both researchers and RMs, and B) gathering insights from upper-management staff at universities regarding OS and Knowledge Valorisation (KV) practices. The responses from the upper-management questions were intended to provide valuable information for creating the action plans for embedding and accelerating knowledge valorisation good practices at universities (Task 1.5). These insights will be discussed and elaborated upon in Deliverable 1.5, which is expected to be completed by July 2025.

Non-academic actors, researchers and research managers mainly contributed to objective A, by answering questions related to the portfolio of skills and competencies. While upper-management mainly contributed to objective B, by answering questions related to the current status of the promotion of OS and KV at Universities.

Following this, the survey underwent an ethics review and was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Autonomous University of Barcelona. Upon receiving approval, it was officially launched the 17th of June 2024.

4.5 Data collection

The initial plan was to conduct the survey in two iterations, launched in mid-June and late June, aiming to collect data by the first week of July and allowing time for data processing by early September. However, due to varying summer holiday periods among consortium members and the challenge of obtaining a meaningful number of responses in such a short time span, the consortium agreed to launch additional iterations addressing the different needs from participating ecosystems from mid-July until early September.

Despite the efforts to identify stakeholders, the tailoring of the survey's language and length, and the addition of survey iterations, obtaining responses proved challenging, particularly from non-academic sectors and specially businesses.

Additionally, the ongoing situation in the Middle East significantly hindered engagement in the territory. With challenges experienced to interact with the stakeholders, and provided that the ecosystem is considered to be “naïve” on the survey topics, the consortium agreed with the University of Haifa that the limited data obtained there would not be considered for survey analysis and conclusions generation, but for validation purposes only.

Regardless of all challenges experienced, a total of 103 responses were gathered, including researchers, RMs, business, public administration, civil society and upper-management staff from the Karlstad Universitet, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Bologna Università, and Université de Lorraine. More Information about the survey participants can be found In Annex 2.

5 Results and Discussion

The following section provides a summary of the main survey findings regarding the skills of researchers and RMs, as perceived by quadruple helix actors. It focuses on key results obtained for both researchers and RMs profiles in the areas evaluated: systemic vision, collaboration, and impact. For each of these areas, the section highlights the percentage of acceptance for the relevant skills, additional competencies that were emphasized and the main strengths and weaknesses identified. A final summary table and graph is included for each area. The analysis was performed grouping the data in three groups: researchers, research managers, and non-academic actors.

5.1 Researchers' skills

This section outlines the specific skills and competencies essential for researchers to effectively engage in OS and KV practices. It details the competences identified in each of the three key areas: systemic vision, collaboration and impact.

5.1.1 Systemic vision

Researchers' skills relevant to systemic vision: As shown in Table 1, the researchers' skills relevant to systemic vision, which were accepted by more than 95% of survey participants, include strategic thinking, systemic thinking, abstract thinking, and critical thinking. Although analytical thinking and problem-solving did not reach the 95% threshold, a similar acceptance percentage was observed among external stakeholders and researchers.

Table 1: Acceptance of the pre-selection of researchers' skills as relevant to systemic vision, %

Skill	Civil society, private sector and public sector	RMs	Researchers	All stakeholders
Strategic thinking	100%	100%	96,77%	98,90%
Systemic thinking	96,67%	100%	96,77%	97,80%
Abstract thinking	100%	93,33%	96,77%	96,70%
Critical thinking	100%	96,67%	93,55%	96,70%
Analytical thinking	93,33%	96,67%	93,55%	94,51%
Problem solving	90%	96,67%	93,55%	94,51%

Additional skills relevant to systemic vision: The following three tables (tables 2, 3 and 4) summarize stakeholder reflections on the addition of key skills essential for adopting a systemic vision. Beyond

the previously identified skills—strategic, systemic, abstract, and critical thinking—stakeholders highlighted other crucial competencies, including decision-making, empathy, emotional intelligence, and ecological thinking.

Of particular interest, empathy, caring and emotional skills closely align with competences in the LifeComp framework, such as empathy, well-being and self-regulation. Similarly, ecological thinking resonates with competencies from the GreenComp framework, specifically those related to acting for sustainability. Also, computational thinking is mentioned aligning with competences included in the DigComp.

Skills previously associated with collaboration and impact, such as creativity, interdisciplinary research, and communication, were also mentioned in this context, underscoring their relevance for fostering a systemic vision.

Table 2: Additional skills relevant to systemic vision suggested by the civil society, private sector and public sector

Skills not included in the pre-selection of Open Science skills	Skills not included in the pre-selection of skills related to systemic vision	Alignment with existing competence frameworks
Decision making		
	Collaboration	Collaboration**
	Communication skills	Communicate to the broad public* Communication**
	Creativity	Creativity*
Empathy		Empathy** Ensure well-being at work*
Adaptive research (learning evaluation)		Evaluate research* Flexibility** Managing learning**
	Transformative oriented thinking and social impact action	Increase the impact of science on policy & society*
	Traditional and/or non-academic knowledge analysis	Promote citizen science*
	Multistakeholder comprehensive approach in all phases of research process	Promote citizen science*
	Facilitation and Orchestration	Promote citizen science*
Emotional thinking		Self-regulation** Ensure well-being at work*
Ecological thinking		Valuing sustainability***
	Ability to work in group and actually knowing how to share resources	Work in teams*
Writing skills		Write research documents*

Notes: *ResearchComp, **LifeComp, ***GreenComp

Table 3: Additional skills relevant to systemic vision suggested by the RMs

Skills not included in the pre-selection of Open Science skills	Skills not included in the pre-selection of skills related to systemic vision	Alignment with existing competence frameworks
	Audience awareness	<i>Communicate to the broad public*</i>
	Communication skills	<i>Communicate to the broad public*</i>
	<i>Creativity</i>	<i>Creativity*</i>
	Networking thinking	<i>Increase the impact of science on policy and society*</i> <i>Promote the transfer of knowledge*</i> <i>Develop networks*</i>
Research culture		<i>Perform scientific research*</i>
	Design thinking	<i>Promote open innovation*</i>
Writing skills		<i>Write research documents*</i>

Notes: *ResearchComp

Table 4: Additional skills relevant to systemic vision suggested by the researchers

Skills not included in the pre-selection of Open Science skills	Skills not included in the pre-selection of skills related to systemic vision	Alignment with existing competence frameworks
Administrative thinking		
Computational thinking		<i>Browsing, searching and filtering data, information and digital content* **</i> <i>Evaluating data, information and digital content***</i> <i>Managing data, information and digital content*</i>
	Cross-disciplinary thinking	<i>Conduct interdisciplinary research*</i>
	Interdisciplinarity	<i>Conduct interdisciplinary research*</i>
	Intercultural communication competences	<i>Interact professionally*</i>
Lateral thinking (Edward DeBono)		
7 hats		
	Network	<i>Develop networks*</i>
Practical insights		
	Communication skills	<i>Communicate to the broad public*</i>
Responsible thinking		<i>Have disciplinary expertise*</i>
	Strategies to lead processes of co-creation with social actors and the society at large	<i>Promote citizen science*</i>
	Creativity	<i>Creativity*</i>
	Values	<i>Apply research ethics and integrity principles*</i>

Caring		Well-being** Ensure well-being at work*
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Notes: *ResearchComp, **LifeComp, ****DigComp

Main strengths and weaknesses to systemic vision: Regarding the current strengths of researchers, analytical thinking and critical thinking rank among the top three skills consistently highlighted by all representatives of the quadruple helix (Figure 7). However, when it comes to areas for improvement (Figure 8), strategic thinking and systemic thinking emerge as two key competencies that require further development. The emphasis on both developing strategic and systemic thinking reflects a shift toward fostering leadership and adaptability within research careers, which is increasingly important for addressing the evolving demands of innovation ecosystems.

Figure 7: Perception about the best acquired skills by researchers related to systemic vision

Figure 8: Perception about the skills to be improved by researchers related to systemic vision

Summary for Systemic vision skills for researchers: The following figure represents the main results obtained for systemic vision skills for researchers.

Key Skills	Additional skills suggested	Best acquired skills	Skills to be improved
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Abstract thinking •Critical thinking •Strategic thinking •Systemic thinking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Administrative thinking •Caring •Computational thinking •Creativity •Decision making •Ecological thinking •Emotional thinking •Empathy •Lateral thinking •7 hats •Responsible thinking •Writing skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Analytical thinking •Critical thinking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Strategic thinking •Systemic thinking

Figure 9: Summary of systemic vision skills for researchers

5.1.2 Collaboration

Researchers' skills relevant to collaboration: As indicated in Table 5, the skills regarded as essential for collaboration, endorsed by more than 95% of survey participants, include professional interaction, conducting interdisciplinary research, teamwork, promoting inclusion and diversity, and building networks. These skills demonstrate a shared understanding across both academic and non-academic stakeholders of the importance of effective communication, cooperation, and fostering diverse and inclusive environments.

However, skills such as resource mobilization, negotiation, and creativity are viewed differently by academic actors—particularly researchers—and their non-academic counterparts. This discrepancy may stem from a more pronounced emphasis within academic environments on research-specific competencies, often prioritizing scholarly expertise over essential skills related to resource management and negotiation. These latter skills are typically associated with leadership, project funding, and administrative functions. In contrast, these skills were recognized as highly relevant by non-academic stakeholders, highlighting a potential gap in perceptions between academic and non-academic sectors regarding the broader skill set needed for successful collaboration. Non-academic actors may place greater emphasis on resource mobilization and negotiation due to their closer involvement with industry, government, and other sectors where these skills are critical for driving innovation and organizational growth.

This contrast underlines the need for fostering a more balanced approach, where researchers are better equipped with practical, cross-sectoral skills to engage effectively with the wider innovation ecosystem.

Table 5: Acceptance of the pre-selection of researchers' skills as relevant to collaboration, %

Skill	Civil society, private sector and public sector	RMs	Researchers	All stakeholders
Interact professionally	96,67%	96,67%	100%	98,90%
Conduct interdisciplinary research	100%	96,67%	96,77%	97,80%
Work in teams	96,67%	100%	96,77%	97,80%
Promote inclusion & diversity	100%	100%	90,32%	96,70%
Develop networks	93,33%	96,67%	100%	96,70%
Mobilise resources	100%	90%	93,55%	94,51%
Negotiate	96,67%	100%	87,10%	94,51%
Creativity	96,67%	93,33%	90,32%	93,41%

Additional skills relevant to collaboration: The following three tables (Tables 6, 7, and 8) summarize stakeholders' reflections on the addition of key skills essential for collaboration. Notably, delegation, empathy, and the request to change the wording from "negotiate" to "generate consensus" are highlighted by stakeholders. Additionally, skills that align closely with the LifeComp framework, such as empathy or flexibility, are identified as essential. The capacity for multi-stakeholder collaboration and communication skills are also suggest the importance of inclusivity and the ability to navigate complex social dynamics.

Table 6: Additional skills relevant to collaboration suggested by the civil society, private sector and public sector

Skills not included in the pre-selection of Open Science skills	Skills not included in the pre-selection of skills related to collaboration	Alignment with existing competence frameworks
	Live implementation and experimentation: mobilise co-created knowledge into practice	<i>Promote citizen science*</i> <i>Promote open innovation*</i>
	Conduct multi-stakeholder collaboration (among policymakers, researchers, industries, communities and civil society to co-create innovative solutions)	<i>Promote citizen science*</i> <i>Promote open innovation*</i>
	Communication skills	<i>Communication to the broad public*</i>
Delegation		
	Reliability	<i>Manage research data*</i> <i>Promote citizen science*</i> <i>Perform scientific research*</i>
Empathy		<i>Empathy**</i> <i>Ensure wellbeing at work*</i>
	Have a prestigeless approach within the team	<i>Work in teams*</i>

Skills not included in the pre-selection of Open Science skills	Skills not included in the pre-selection of skills related to collaboration	Alignment with existing competence frameworks
Change the term negotiate to generate consensus		
	How to share your own research	<i>Disseminate results to the research community*</i> <i>Communicate to the broad public*</i> <i>Promote the transfer of knowledge*</i>
	Collaborative leadership	<i>Interact professionally*</i>
	Conflict management	<i>Manage projects*</i> <i>Work in teams*</i>
	Personal communication	<i>Communication**</i> <i>Communication to the broad public*</i>

Notes: *ResearchComp, **LifeComp

Table 7: Additional skills relevant to collaboration suggested by the RMs

Skills not included in the pre-selection of Open Science skills	Skills not included in the pre-selection of skills related to collaboration	Alignment with existing competence frameworks
Empathy		<i>Empathy**</i> <i>Ensure wellbeing at work*</i>
Flexibility		<i>Flexibility**</i>
	Social impact measurement	<i>Increase the impact of science on policy & society*</i>
	Work with the 4 th helix – more relation with society in order to orientate the research to the social needs	<i>Promote citizen science*</i>

Notes: *ResearchComp, **LifeComp

Table 8: Additional skills relevant to collaboration suggested by the researchers

Skills not included in the pre-selection of skills related to collaboration	Alignment with existing competence frameworks
Values, ethics, caring	<i>Apply research ethics and integrity principles;</i> <i>Ensure wellbeing at work*</i>
Co-creation strategies	<i>Promote citizen science*</i>
Communication skills	<i>Communication**</i> <i>Communicate to the broad public*</i>

Notes: *ResearchComp, **LifeComp

Main strengths and weaknesses to collaboration: When examining the current strengths of researchers in the context of collaboration, develop networks, interact professionally and work in teams rank among the top three competencies identified by all representatives from the quadruple

helix model (Figure 10). This suggests that researchers possess a strong foundation in building connections and fostering professional relationships. On the contrary, as reflected in Figure 11, conduct interdisciplinary research and promote inclusion & diversity have been identified as top priorities for skill enhancement among researchers, these skills haven't been previously recognized as essential for collaboration, being essential for navigating the complexities of modern research challenges, which often require insights from multiple disciplines and perspectives.

Figure 10: Best acquired skills by researchers related to collaboration

Figure 11: Perception about the skills to be improved by researchers related to collaboration

Summary for Collaboration skills for researchers: Figure 12 highlights the main results obtained for the collaboration area.

Key skills	Additional skills suggested	Best acquired skills	Skills to be improved
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Conduct interdisciplinary research •Interact professionally •Work in teams •Promote inclusion & diversity •Develop networks •Mobilise resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Delegation •Empathy •Change the term negotiate to generate consensus •Flexibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Develop networks •Interact professionally •Work in teams 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Conduct interdisciplinary research •Promote inclusion & diversity

Figure 12: Main findings of the collaboration area for researchers

5.1.3 Impact

Researchers' skills relevant to Impact: Regarding the skills related to impact (Table 9) a consensus is reached regarding the skills of promoting transfer of knowledge, apply research ethics and integrity, increase impact of science on policy & society, manage research data, promote open innovation, communicate to broad public and promote open access publications. Additionally, all representatives from civil society, the private sector, and the public sector identified the ability to teach in academic or vocational contexts as a relevant skill for maximizing impact. This underscores the importance of education and training in translating research into practical applications. Also, the promotion of citizen science and manage intellectual property are highlighted by external stakeholders.

Table 9: Acceptance of the pre-selection of researchers' skills as relevant to impact, %

Skill	Civil society, private sector and public sector	Research Managers	Researchers	All stakeholders
Promote the transfer of knowledge	100%	100%	96,77%	98,90%
Apply research ethics and integrity principles	100%	96,67%	96,77%	97,80%

Skill	Civil society, private sector and public sector	Research Managers	Researchers	All stakeholders
Increase impact of science on policy & society	100%	100%	93,55%	97,80%
Manage research data	100%	96,67%	96,77%	97,80%
Promote open innovation	100%	96,67%	87,10%	96,70%
Communicate to the broad public	96,67%	100%	93,55%	96,70%
Promote open access publications	100%	93,33%	93,55%	95,60%
Teach in academic or vocational contexts	100%	96,67%	80,65%	92,31%
Disseminate results to the research community	93,33%	86,67%	96,77%	92,31%
Promote citizen science	96,67%	93,33%	87,10%	92,31%
Manage intellectual property rights	96,67%	93,33%	83,87%	91,21%
Show entrepreneurial spirit	86,67%	80%	70,97%	80,22%

Additional skills relevant to Impact: Stakeholders from public, private, civil society, and academic sectors (Table 10) have emphasized additional key skills for impact. These include promoting continuous learning and adaptive evaluation to navigate a rapidly evolving field, as well as enhancing social analysis skills aligned with the ResearchComp framework to engage effectively with diverse communities. Strategic sustainability, linked to GreenComp and competence such as futures literacy and political agency, is also prioritized to ensure environmentally responsible practices within research and innovation.

Table 10: Additional skills relevant to impact suggested

Type of stakeholder	Skills not included in the pre-selection of Open Science skills	Skills not included in the pre-selection of skills related to impact	Alignment with existing competence frameworks
	Promote learning and adaptive evaluation		<i>Evaluate research*</i> <i>Adaptability****</i>

Type of stakeholder	Skills not included in the pre-selection of Open Science skills	Skills not included in the pre-selection of skills related to impact	Alignment with existing competence frameworks
Civil society, the private sector and the public sector		Adaptability	<i>Cope with pressure*</i> <i>Plan self-organisation*</i> <i>Negotiate*</i>
	Social analysis		<i>Have disciplinary expertise*</i>
Research Managers	Strategic sustainability		<i>Futures literacy****</i> <i>Political agency****</i>

Notes: *ResearchComp, ****GreenComp

Main strengths and weaknesses to Impact: When evaluating researchers' current strengths and areas for improvement in generating societal impact, both external stakeholders, RMs, and researchers themselves show a strong consensus on key competencies and gaps. The top strengths (figure 13) consistently highlighted by these groups include the abilities to disseminate research findings within academic circles, manage research data effectively, and teach within academic or vocational contexts. These skills are central to researchers' core activities, ensuring robust knowledge-sharing within the scientific community, maintaining high standards of data integrity, and educating future generations of researchers and professionals.

In contrast, there is also widespread agreement on the primary areas where researchers could enhance their impact beyond the academic sphere (figure 14). All stakeholder groups identified area where societal engagement is key such as communication with the general, increasing the influence of research on policy and society and promoting citizen science.

Figure 13: Perception about the best acquired skills by researchers related to impact

Figure 14: Perception about the skills to be improved by researchers related to impact

Summary for Impact skills for researchers: Figure 15 highlights the main results obtained when Identifying skills to generate Impact

Key skills	Best acquired skills	Skills to be improved	Additional skills suggested
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Promote the transfer of knowledge •Apply research ethics and integrity principles •Increase impact of science on policy and society •Manage research data •Promote open innovation •Communicate to the broad public •Promote open access publications •Teach in academic or vocational contexts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Disseminate results to the research community •Manage research data •Promote the transfer of knowledge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Communicate to the broad public •Increase impact of science on policy & society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Promote learning and adaptive evaluation •Social analysis •Strategic sustainability

Figure 15: Summary for impact skills for researchers

5.2 Research managers' skills

This section outlines the essential skills and competencies required for RMs, categorized into three key areas: systemic vision, collaboration, and impact. Each area highlights the specific skills identified as crucial for effectively supporting open science and fostering innovation in research environments.

5.2.1 Systemic vision

Research managers' skills relevant to systemic vision: The Research managers' skills relevant to systemic vision (Table 11) accepted by more than 95% of the survey participants are cultural sensibility, strategic planning, problem solving, critical thinking and decision making. Therefore, all the pre-selected skills by the KALEIDOS consortium will be considered for the Open Science Profile for RMs.

There are deeper differences in the perspective to the relevance of problem solving and critical thinking. Problem solving is considered relevant by all non-academic actors and RMs, in contrast to the 93,55% of researchers. Critical thinking is considered relevant by all non-academic actors, 96,77% of researchers and 93,33% of RMs. As RMs are the target of these skills, it is important to focus on the awareness raising of the importance of critical thinking for their work.

Table 11: Acceptance of the pre-selection of Research Managers' skills as relevant to systemic vision, %

Skill	Civil society, private sector and public sector	Researchers	Research Managers	All stakeholders
Cultural sensibility	100%	100%	96,67%	98,90%
Strategic planning	96,67%	100%	100%	98,90%
Problem solving	100%	93,55%	100%	97,80%
Critical thinking	100%	96,77%	93,33%	96,70%
Decision making	96,67%	96,77%	96,67%	96,70%

Additional skills relevant to systemic vision: Considering the perspective from all survey participants, there are two suggested additional competencies to highlight related to systemic vision: systems thinking and empathy. Systems thinking is mentioned in the GreenComp, and it is defined as “to approach a [...] problem from all sides; to consider time, space and context in order to understand how elements interact within and between systems”¹². Empathy is mentioned in the LifeComp, and it is defined as “the understanding of another person’s emotions, experiences and values, and the provision of appropriate responses”¹³.

From the additional skills suggested by the non-academic actors to consider as relevant to systemic vision, only research financial management is aligned with the RMComp, in particular with the competency research finance. The others are aligned with the LifeComp (managing learning, empathy, wellbeing) and/or the GreenComp (systems thinking, critical thinking and problem framing). In addition, they propose to include “the possibility to be open to discussion and to receive feedback as well”, which is not mentioned in any of these competence frameworks (see Table 12). Researchers propose five additional skills to consider. “Administrative thinking”, “project management” and

¹² <https://publications.irc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC128040>

¹³ https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/lifecomp/lifecomp-conceptual-reference-model_en

"ethical aspects" are aligned with the RMComp (with pre-award post-award, research project management, and research ethics and integrity respectively; "social competencies" is aligned with the LifeComp (empathy, collaboration and communication); and they propose to include "co-creation", which is not mentioned in any of these competence frameworks (see Table 13). And RMs themselves, suggested to add "systemic, analytical and abstract thinking" (aligned with the GreenComp competence systems thinking) and "written and oral communication" (aligned with several competencies considered in RMComp, such as preparing and writing reports (including evaluation reports and funder reports), to the list of relevant skills related to systemic vision (see Table 14).

Table 12: Additional skills relevant to systemic vision suggested by the civil society, the private sector and the public sector

Skills not included in the pre-selection of Open Science skills	Skills not included in the pre-selection of skills related to systemic vision	Alignment with existing competence frameworks
	Collaborative leadership	<i>Change management*</i> <i>Coaching skills*</i> <i>Collaboration**</i>
	Communication skills	<i>Communication**</i> <i>Building and maintaining relationships with research funders, partners or other stakeholders*</i> <i>Designing and implementing research communication plans*</i> <i>Media liaison and associated activities*</i> <i>Preparing and writing reports (including evaluation reports and funder reports) *</i> <i>Social media engagement*</i>
Community sensibility that includes detection of stakeholders to be involved to achieve transformation and favours learning and experimentation		<i>Managing learning**</i>
Empathy		<i>Empathy**</i>
PESTEL analysis, environmental analysis (strategy)		<i>Well-being**</i> <i>Systems thinking****</i> <i>Critical thinking****</i> <i>Problem framing****</i>
Research financial management		<i>Research finance*</i>
Systemic thinking understanding		<i>Systems thinking****</i>
The possibility to be open to discussion and to receive feedback as well		

Notes: *RMComp, **LifeComp, ****GreenComp

Table 13: Additional skills relevant to systemic vision suggested by the researchers

Skills not included in the pre-selection of Open Science skills	Skills not included in the pre-selection of skills related to systemic vision	Alignment with existing competence frameworks
Administrative thinking		<i>Pre-Award Post-Award*</i>
Social competences		<i>Empathy** Collaboration** Communication**</i>
	Values	<i>Cultural sensibility* Community engagement with research*</i>
Co-creation		
Ethical aspects		<i>Research ethics and Integrity*</i>
	Team management	<i>People Management and managing team performance*</i>
Project Management		<i>Research Project Management*</i>

Notes: *RMComp, **LifeComp

Table 14: Additional skills relevant to systemic vision suggested by the research managers

Skills not included in the pre-selection of Open Science skills	Skills not included in the pre-selection of skills related to systemic vision	Alignment with existing competence frameworks
	Complexity management	<i>Professional flexibility* Change management* Flexibility** Systems thinking**** Critical thinking**** Problem framing****</i>
	Connector – assist in increasing networks	<i>Academic community relationship collaboration* Community engagement with research* Engagement with key stakeholders*</i>
	Creativity	<i>Creativity*</i>
	Professional flexibility	<i>Professional flexibility* Flexibility**</i>
	Know your rules! Both institute and programme	<i>Strategic planning*</i>
	Negotiate	<i>Pre-Award Post-Award* Engagement with key stakeholders* Building and maintaining relationships with research funders, partners, or other stakeholders* Handling difficult conversations and partnerships*</i>

Systemic, Analytical and Abstract Thinking		Systems thinking****
Written and oral communication		<i>Communication**</i> <i>Building and maintaining relationships with research funders, partners or other stakeholders*</i> <i>Designing and implementing research communication plans*</i> <i>Media liaison and associated activities*</i> <i>Preparing and writing reports (including evaluation reports and funder reports) *</i> <i>Social media engagement*</i>

Notes: *RMComp, **LifeComp

Main strengths and weaknesses to systemic vision: Regarding current strengths of RMs related to systemic vision, decision making, problem solving and strategic planning are among the top 3 skills highlighted by all representatives from the quadruple helix (figure 16). Regarding the skills to be improved by RMs, cultural sensibility and strategic planning are among the top 3 skills highlighted (figure 17). Therefore, even if they are considered to be good at strategic planning, there is still room for improvement. Regarding cultural sensibility, several actions can be undertaken, such as offering foreign languages training, and joint training opportunities with RMs from other countries, taking advantage of the Erasmus staff mobility funding available.

Figure 16: Perception about the best acquired skills by RMs related to systemic vision

Figure 17: Perception about the skills to improve by research managers related to systemic vision

Summary for systemic vision skills for Research Managers: Figure 18 highlights the main results obtained for systemic vision skills for RMs.

Key skills	Additional skills suggested	Best acquired skills	Skills to be improved
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decision making • Critical thinking • Cultural sensibility • Problem solving • Strategic planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administrative thinking • Co-creation • Community sensibility that includes detection of stakeholders to be involved to achieve transformation and favours learning and experimentation • Creativity • Empathy • PESTEL analysis, environmental analysis (strategy) • Project Management • Research financial management • Social competences • Systemic, Analytical and Abstract Thinking • The possibility to be open to discussion and to receive feedback as well • Written and oral communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decision making • Problem solving • Strategic planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural sensibility • Strategic planning

Figure 18: Summary of systemic vision skills for research managers

5.2.2 Collaboration

Researcher Managers' skills relevant to collaboration: The RMs' skills relevant to collaboration, as detailed in table 15, accepted by more than 95% of the survey participants are: building and maintaining relationships with research funders, partners, or other stakeholders; building trust within relevant research and strategic partnerships; diplomacy, negotiation, and mediation skills; people management and managing team performance; professional flexibility; team building; handling difficult conversations and partnerships; managing equality, diversity and inclusion (including gender, disability and racism); and coaching skills. In addition, representatives from the civil society, the private sector and the public sector consider business and commercial liaison management to be relevant to collaboration, in contrast to 90,32% of researchers and 86,67% of RMs.

Further research could be undertaken to get a deeper understanding of the difference of perceptions between the non-academic and the academic actors on this matter, as the collaboration between the academia and the private sector is key for the success of many research projects. One aspect to consider could be: Who is in charge of business and commercial liaison management at universities? It might be that the ones in charge are not considered to be RMs.

Table 15: Acceptance of the pre-selection of RMs' skills as relevant to collaboration, %

Skill	Civil society, private sector and public sector	Researchers	Research Managers	All stakeholders
Building and maintaining relationships with research funders, partners, or other stakeholders	100%	100%	100%	100%
Building trust within relevant research and strategic partnerships	100%	100%	100%	100%
Diplomacy, negotiation, and mediation skills	100%	96,77%	100%	98,90%
People Management and managing team performance	100%	100%	96,67%	98,90%
Professional flexibility	96,67%	100%	100%	98,90%
Team building	96,67%	100%	100%	98,90%
Handling difficult conversations and partnerships	100%	96,77%	96,67%	97,80%
Managing equality, diversity and inclusion (including gender, disability and racism)	100%	96,77%	93,33%	96,70%
Coaching skills	96,67%	100%	93,33%	96,70%
Creativity	93,33%	96,77%	90%	93,41%
Business and commercial liaison management	100%	90,32%	86,67%	92,31%

Additional skills relevant to collaboration: Considering the perspective from all survey participants, the additional competencies suggested aligned with RMComp are related to the competence areas subject matter expertise and research project oversight/management. Furthermore, the competence empathy from the LifeComp, is also suggested by the non-academic actors.

From the additional skills suggested by the non-academic actors (table 16) to consider as relevant to collaboration, only budgetary, financial basis is aligned with the RMComp (research finance). “Empathy” is aligned with the LifeComp (empathy) and the rest are not mentioned in any of these competence frameworks: “assertiveness”, “impartiality”, “patience” and “training on transformative innovation”. “Transformative innovation policy” is defined by Steinmueller as “an approach and a set of methods for

addressing our current failings to move towards a more sustainable and socially just future”¹⁴. The Researchers (table 17) propose two additional skills to consider, aligned to the RMComp research project oversight/management competence area and the competency research ethics and integrity. And RMs themselves (table 17), suggested to add establishing research project plans, also aligned with the RMComp.

Table 16: Additional skills relevant to collaboration suggested by the civil society, the private sector and the public sector

Skills not included in the pre-selection of Open Science skills	Skills not included in the pre-selection of skills related to collaboration	Alignment with existing competence frameworks
	Adaptability	<i>Adaptability****</i> <i>Cultural sensibility*</i> <i>Professional flexibility*</i> <i>Flexibility**</i>
Assertiveness		
Budgetary, financial basis		<i>Research Finance*</i>
	Capacity of communicating with the media	<i>Research Outreach*</i> <i>Designing and implementing research, communication plans*</i> <i>Media liaison and associated activities*</i>
Empathy		<i>Empathy**</i>
	Facilitate co-creation and co-design of living labs within and with the university units	<i>Community engagement with research*</i>
	Facilitate the researchers meet stakeholders from the [quadruple helix]	<i>Community engagement with research*</i> <i>Engagement with key stakeholders*</i>
Impartiality		
Patience		

¹⁴ Steinmueller, E. (2022) Transformative Innovation Policy Resource Lab, User Guide. Available at <https://tipresource.net/resource/tip-resource-lab-user-guide/>

Skills not included in the pre-selection of Open Science skills	Skills not included in the pre-selection of skills related to collaboration	Alignment with existing competence frameworks
	Promotion of collective thinking in the university community	<i>Academic community relationship collaboration*</i>
Training on transformative /innovation		

Table 17: Additional skills relevant to collaboration suggested by the researchers and the Research Managers

Type of stakeholder	Skills not included in the pre-selection of Open Science skills	Skills not included in the pre-selection of skills related to collaboration	Alignment with existing competence frameworks
Researchers	Administrative skills		<i>Research Project Management*</i> <i>Managing research project deliverables*</i> <i>Designing monitoring and evaluation frameworks and indicators*</i> <i>Establishing research project plans*</i>
	Ethics		<i>Research ethics and integrity*</i>
Research Managers	Establishing research project plans		<i>Establishing research project plans*</i>

Notes: *RMComp

Main strengths and weaknesses to collaboration: Regarding current strengths of RMs related to collaboration, building and maintaining relationships with research funders and other stakeholders, professional flexibility, and building trust within relevant research and strategic partnerships are among the top 3 skills highlighted by all representatives from the quadruple helix (figure 19). And regarding the skills to be improved by RMs, managing equality, diversity and inclusion (including gender, disability and racism) are among the top 3 skills highlighted (figure 20).

Figure 19: Perception about the best acquired skills by RMs related to collaboration

Figure 20: Perception about the skills to improve by the research managers related to collaboration

Summary for collaboration skills for RMs: Figure 21 highlights the main results for collaboration skills for RMs.

Key skills	Additional skills suggested	Best acquired skills	Skills to be improved
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building and maintaining relationships with research funders and other stakeholders • Building trust within relevant research and strategic partnerships • Business and commercial liaison management • Diplomacy, negotiation, and mediation skills • People Management and managing team performance • Professional flexibility • Team building • Handling difficult conversations and partnerships • Managing equality, diversity and inclusion (including gender, disability and racism) • Coaching skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assertiveness • Budgetary, financial basis • Capacity of communicating with the media • Empathy • Impartiality • Patience • Training on transformative innovation • Administrative skills • Ethics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building and maintaining relationships with research funders and other stakeholders • Building trust within relevant research and strategic partnerships • Professional flexibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Managing equality, diversity and inclusion (including gender, disability and racism)

Figure 21: Summary for Collaboration skills for research managers

5.2.3 Impact

Researchers Managers' skills relevant to Impact: The RMs' skills relevant to impact (table 18) accepted by more than 95% of the survey participants are academic community relationship collaboration, community engagement with research, engagement with key stakeholders, research outreach, technology transfer, designing and implementing research communication plans, monitoring and evaluation frameworks and indicators, and provision of training for outreach engagement.

Table 18: Acceptance of the pre-selection of research managers' skills as relevant to impact, %

Skill	Civil society, private sector and public sector	Researchers	Research Managers	All stakeholders
Academic community relationship collaboration	100%	100%	100%	100%
Community engagement with research	100%	100%	100%	100%
Engagement with key stakeholders	100%	100%	100%	100%
Research outreach	100%	100%	100%	100%

Skill	Civil society, private sector and public sector	Researchers	Research Managers	All stakeholders
Technology transfer	100%	100%	96,67%	98,90%
Designing and implementing research communication plans	96,67%	100%	96,67%	97,80%
Monitoring and evaluation frameworks and indicators	96,67%	96,77%	96,67%	96,70%
Provision of training for outreach engagement	96,67%	96,77%	93,33%	95,60%
Social media Engagement	93,33%	96,77%	93,33%	93,41%

Additional skills relevant to Impact: Considering the perspective from all survey participants, the additional competences suggested aligned with RMComp, the LifeComp and the GreenComp. Four of the additional skills suggested by the non-academic actors to consider as relevant to impact are aligned with the RMComp (media associated activities, pre-award post-award, research ethics and integrity); “continuous learning” is aligned with the LifeComp (managing learning) and "digitalisation" is aligned with the DigComp competence area communication and collaboration (see table 19). The researchers propose two additional skills to consider. "Social caring, people caring, welfare and also ethics" is aligned with the RMComp competency research ethics and integrity and the LifeComp competency well-being and "issues of sustainability" is aligned with the GreenComp competence area act for sustainability. And RMs themselves, suggested to add "capacity building and training skills (not only for outreach engagement)", aligned with the RMComp (provision of training for outreach engagement) and LifeComp (managing learning) (see table 20).

Table 19: Additional skills relevant to impact suggested by the civil society, the private sector and the public sector

Skills not included in the pre-selection of Open Science skills	Skills not included in the pre-selection of skills related to impact	Alignment with existing competence frameworks
Emphasize and make visible existing initiatives that are transformative research and innovation		
Continuous learning		<i>Managing learning**</i>

Skills not included in the pre-selection of Open Science skills	Skills not included in the pre-selection of skills related to impact	Alignment with existing competence frameworks
Digitalisation		<i>Interacting through digital technologies*** Sharing through digital technologies*** Collaborating through digital technologies***</i>
Engagement with media		<i>Media associated activities*</i>
Search for both public and private financing resources		<i>Pre-Award Post-Award*</i>
Social media involvement must also include strict regulation of content		<i>Research Ethics and Integrity*</i>
	Team building	<i>Team building*</i>

Notes: *RMComp **LifeComp ***DigComp

Table 20: Additional skills relevant to impact suggested by the researchers and the research managers

Type of stakeholder	Skills not included in the pre-selection of Open Science skills	Skills not included in the pre-selection of skills related to impact	Alignment with existing competence frameworks
Researchers	Social caring, people caring, welfare and also ethics		<i>Research Ethics and Integrity* Well-being**</i>
	Issues of sustainability		<i>Collective action**** Individual initiative****</i>
Research Managers	Capacity building and training skills (not only for outreach engagement)		<i>Managing Learning** Provision of training for outreach engagement*</i>

Notes: *RMComp **LifeComp ****GreenComp

Main strengths and weaknesses to Impact: Regarding current strengths of RMs related to impact, academic community relationship collaboration and monitoring and evaluation frameworks and indicators are among the top 3 skills highlighted by all representatives from the quadruple helix (figure 22). And regarding the skills to be improved by RMs, social media engagement is among the top 3 skills highlighted (figure 23).

Figure 22: Perception about the best acquired skills by RMs related to impact

Figure 23: Perception about the skills to improve by RMs related to impact

Summary for impact skills for RMs: Figure 24 highlights the main results for Impact skills for RMs.

Key skills	Additional skills suggested	Best acquired skills	Skills to be improved
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academic community relationship collaboration • Community engagement with research • Designing and implementing research communication plans • Engagement with key stakeholders • Monitoring and evaluation frameworks and indicators • Provision of training for outreach engagement • Research outreach • Technology transfer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphasize and make visible existing initiatives that are transformative research and innovation • Continuous learning • Digitalisation • Engagement with media • Search for both public and private financing resources • Social media involvement must also include strict regulation of content • Social caring, people caring, welfare and also ethics • Issues of sustainability • Capacity building and training skills (not only for outreach engagement) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academic community relationship collaboration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitoring and evaluation frameworks and indicators

Figure 24: Summary for impact skills for research managers

6 Validation

To ensure the accuracy and relevance of the findings and results presented in this deliverable, a comprehensive validation process was undertaken. This process included an initial validation phase, which took place during a face-to-face consortium meeting held in Alicante on November 18, 2024. During this meeting, the main findings and results were presented and discussed in detail with consortium members. This collaborative session provided an opportunity for consortium members to critically review the data, methodologies, and interpretations, ensuring alignment with the project’s objectives. Furthermore, to address potential gaps and ensure representation from underrepresented groups, an additional validation step was conducted through an online, face-to-face interview with external members from the business sector (Anais Le Corvec, CEO and Co-Founder at Cliclab Transformative Agent). This sector had been identified as underrepresented in the survey responses collected earlier in the project. The external experts provided valuable insights, particularly regarding data processing methodologies and practical applications of the findings.

The comments, suggestions, and recommendations gathered during these validation steps have been carefully analysed and integrated into this final version of the deliverable. Key adjustments include refinements in the data processing approach and the inclusion of additional contextual comments to enhance clarity and applicability.

7 Open Science skills for researchers and research managers

The following section presents a visually engaging summary of the main results and findings discussed in the previous section. By translating complex insights into a clear visual format, this section aims to enhance understanding, facilitate comparison, and highlight the key takeaways.

7.1 Open Science skills for researchers

Figure 25: Open Science skills for researchers

RESEARCHERS' SKILLS

Figure 26: Key, best acquired and to be improved researcher's skills relevant for Open Science

For the design of the researchers' training, UAB, in collaboration with the rest of the partners from the consortium, will prioritize to address the skills to be improved: **Strategic thinking, Systemic thinking, Conduct interdisciplinary research, Promote inclusion and diversity, Communicate to the broad public;** and **Increase impact of science on policy and society.**

7.2 Open Science skills for research managers

Figure 27: Open Science skills for research managers

RESEARCHERS MANAGERS' SKILLS

Figure 28: Key, best acquired and to be improved research manager's skills relevant for Open Science

For the design of the research managers' training, KAU, in collaboration with the rest of the partners from the consortium, will prioritize to address the skills to be improved: **Cultural sensibility; Strategic planning; Managing equality, diversity and inclusion; and Monitoring and evaluation frameworks and indicators.**

7.3 Open Science skills for researchers and research managers

Figure 29: Combining Researchers', Research Managers' and shared skills relevant for Open Science

Note: The arrows connect the skills from researchers and research managers which are complementary (see conclusions).

Creativity, Critical thinking, Decision making, Empathy, Managing learning, Well-being, Adaptability and Flexibility are the shared skills among researchers and research managers.

8 Conclusions

This section presents the key conclusions drawn from the initial data processing of the survey results. As outlined in Section 2, the primary objective of this exercise was to identify the essential skills and competencies required by researchers and RMs to advance **open science practices** and facilitate the transition towards **knowledge valorisation** beyond traditional frameworks. These insights will directly inform the design of **KALEIDOS'** pilot training programs for both researchers and RMs.

Quadruple Helix stakeholders expand Researchers' and Research Managers' Competencies with Interdisciplinary, Sustainable, and Digital Skills

As it can be observed in both analyses, for researchers and RMs, **4H stakeholders** identified a number of skills that were not explicitly included in the **ResearchComp** or **RMComp** frameworks, yet they strongly align with the competencies outlined in **GreenComp**, **LifeComp**, and **DigComp**. The skills emphasized by **4H actors** highlight the importance of **interdisciplinarity** and **adaptability** in addressing emerging challenges. Their connection to **GreenComp** emphasizes their role in fostering sustainability and green innovation, while their alignment with **LifeComp** underscores the significance of personal, social, and lifelong learning skills. Moreover, their integration with **DigComp** reflects the growing need for **digital literacy and proficiency** in modern research environments, enabling researchers and RMs to navigate complex technological landscapes. By incorporating these additional competencies, the **4H framework** offers a more comprehensive understanding of the skills required for success in complex, interdisciplinary, and innovation-driven environments. These competencies ensure that both researchers and RMs are not only technically skilled but also equipped to make meaningful contributions to pressing global and societal challenges.

Connecting Research to Society: The Need for LifeComp Skills and Strategic Vision

Regarding researchers, beyond the traditional technical expertise, there is increasing recognition of the value of skills aligned with the **LifeComp**—such as **flexibility**, **empathy**, **managing learning and well-being**. These qualities seem essential for researchers to thrive in today's dynamic, collaborative, and often unpredictable research environments, where interdisciplinary teamwork and stakeholder engagement are key. However, in addition to these personal and interpersonal competencies, the data reflect a growing awareness of a **gap in systemic and strategic vision** among researchers lacking a broader **systemic perspective** that encompasses the larger research ecosystem and its interconnected components. This gap may hinder researchers' ability to understand the broader implications of their work, especially in terms of policy development, societal impact, and long-term sustainability, as it is also perceived in the results. Furthermore, this absence of a strategic vision often results in a disconnect between **research outputs** and **policy influence**, limiting the potential of research to contribute to the shaping of public policies or to address pressing societal challenges. The lack of a clear understanding of how research connects with wider social, economic, and environmental systems can also lead to missed opportunities for fostering **knowledge valorisation**, where the application of research findings extends beyond academia to impact industry, government, and communities in a meaningful way.

Research Managers: Catalysts for Community Engagement and Open Science

The broad spectrum of skills identified for RMs— even after having narrowed down the role of RMs for KALEIDOS project—underscores the crucial importance of their contributions to research and innovation ecosystems. This diversity highlights the need to **professionalise and recognise the value** of RMs' expertise.

The recognition of RMs as key agents of facilitation, responsible for fostering community engagement, building trust, and managing difficult conversations, among other duties, demonstrates their ability to create connections, streamline processes, and foster synergies across diverse stakeholders. This highlights their essential role in advancing open science practices and knowledge valorisation.

Maximizing Impact: The Interplay of Researcher and RM Competencies

A comparative analysis of the skill profiles of researchers and RMs reveals a significant number of complementary skills, as illustrated in Table 21 and Figure 29. These complementary skills emphasize the synergies and interdependencies between the two roles within research and innovation ecosystems. This analysis further reinforces the critical interplay between researchers and RMs, suggesting more **targeted institutional initiatives** that aim to optimize their combined impact and enhance the overall effectiveness of the research and Innovation process.

Table 21: Examples of the complementarity of researchers and research managers

	Researchers' skills	Research Managers' skills
Systemic vision	<i>Strategic thinking:</i> Develop a vision to turn ideas into action. Obtain and synthesize information to identify and explore trends, opportunities, threats (also based on intuition and creativity) to achieve a long-term goal and to thrive in a competitive, changing environment. Identify alternative paths to turn ideas into action, select the most appropriate approach and adjust where necessary.	<i>Strategic planning:</i> The ability to envision and execute a comprehensive research plan aligned with agreed goals and broader organisational and or national/international strategies.
Collaboration	<i>Develop networks:</i> Develop alliances, contacts or partnerships, and exchange information with others. Foster integrated and open collaborations where different stakeholders co-create shared value research and innovations. Develop your personal profile or brand and make yourself visible and accessible in face-to-face and online networking environments.	<i>Building trust within relevant research and strategic partnerships:</i> Build trust within relevant research and strategic partnerships for successful collaboration. Deliver on commitments, foster transparent communication, and prioritise the mutual interests of partners.
	<i>Promote inclusion & diversity:</i> Promote and ensure equality and diversity management, in words as well as in actions and conduct. Guide and advise colleagues about how to work in diverse teams and contexts.	<i>Business and commercial liaison management:</i> Facilitate collaborations between the research team and industry partners or commercial entities. Navigate the intersection of academia and business, identifying opportunities for technology transfer, licensing, or joint ventures.
Impact	<i>Increase the impact of science on policy and society:</i> Increase the impact	<i>Engagement with key stakeholders:</i> Build and sustain collaborative relationships with

Researchers' skills	Research Managers' skills
<p>and use of research findings in policy making, by providing input to and maintaining professional relationships with policymakers and other stakeholders</p>	<p>influential partners, including academic institutions, industry leaders, policymakers, funders, industry, and community representatives</p> <p><i>Monitoring and evaluation frameworks and indicators:</i> Administering systematic processes to assess the progress and impact of research projects and initiatives. Define key performance indicators, establish data collection methods, and implement evaluation frameworks to measure project success. Ensure the effective tracking of research outcomes, facilitating data-driven decision-making and continuous improvement in the research process.</p>
<p><i>Promote open innovation:</i> Apply techniques, models, methods, and strategies that contribute to the promotion of steps towards innovation through collaboration with external people and organizations.</p>	<p><i>Community engagement with research:</i> Establish meaningful connections with diverse communities affected by or interested in the research. Develop strategies for inclusive communication, solicit community input, and ensure the research aligns with community needs and values. Foster open dialogue and collaboration, contribute to the ethical and socially impactful conduct of research, promote community participation and the translation of research outcomes into tangible benefits for the broader community.</p>
<p><i>Promote the transfer of knowledge:</i> Deploy broad awareness and knowledge of processes of knowledge valorisation aimed to maximise the two-way flow of tools, content material, technology, intellectual property, expertise and capability between the research base and relevant stakeholders within the research field.</p>	<p><i>Technology transfer:</i> Facilitate the successful transition of research innovations from the academic, research or laboratory setting to practical applications in the market. Identify commercialisation opportunities, establish collaborations with industry partners, and navigate the legal and regulatory aspects of transferring technologies leading to societal impact and the economic value of research outcomes.</p>

Source: ResearchComp for the researchers' skills and RMComp for the research managers' skills

Annexes

Annex 1. Survey content

Welcome note:

Welcome to the KALEIDOS survey, by sharing your inputs you will contribute to the creation of the Open Science profile for researchers and research managers. It will take you approximately 20 minutes to complete it.

#1 ABOUT KALEIDOS

KALEIDOS is a collaborative project engaging 7 organisations and funded by the European Research Executive Agency. The project will last 2 and a half years and will work with the identified actors such as universities, public bodies, business sector and citizens. The aim of establishing an ongoing dialogue and collaboration with all community members is central.

#2 SUEVEY STRUCTURE

The survey is divided in the following sections:

- About you (Professional profile)
- Researchers' skills
- Research managers' skills
- Open Science
- Knowledge Valorisation
- Personal data

Depending on your professional profile, you will be asked to fill in different sections.

Informed consent:

Thank you for participating in this survey performed by Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB)! A detailed description of how UAB handles personal data is presented in the Privacy Policy that can be accessed here: <https://www.uab.cat/web/about-the-uab/itineraries/data-protection/data-protection-policy-1345828638161.html>

#1 INSTITUTION:

Name: Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

Address: Edifici RR, Pl. Cívica, Campus UAB, Bellaterra, Cerdanyola del Valles, Spain

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#2 RESPONSIBLE PERSONS.

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Role: Principal Investigator

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Role: Project Manager

E-mail: sofia.mojica@uab.cat

#3 WHAT DO WE NEED FROM YOU?

We need you to participate in a short survey. It won't take you more than 20 minutes. Your replies will help us to identify the capacity building needs [and] skills of researchers and research managers to implement open science practices. It will also allow for the enhancement of collaborative work between academic and non-academic actors.

In this context, we need to process some of your personal data:

- Your name and organisation (to know who has already answered the survey and prevent sending unnecessary reminders)

- Some basic demographics (gender, stakeholder group, age range, country of origin, level of education, professional profile)
- Your opinions on the subject matter (anonymously)

#4 WHAT WILL WE DO WITH YOUR DATA?

The survey data will be stored in the EU Survey platform until the deliverable, including the analysis of the data, is approved by the European Commission (September 2025). The data will be anonymised after the closing of the survey in June 2024 and the anonymised data will be gathered in UAB protected server for 5 years after the end of the project (July 2031), and it will be openly available in the trusted repository CORA Repositori de Dades de Recerca.

The project deliverables that the survey will derive will not include your personal data or any other information that could identify you. However, we are obliged to grant access to your data to:

- EU Officials such as our Project Officer for purposes related to project's evaluation;
- EU agencies and other authorities for project's auditing purposes.

#5 HOW CAN YOU WITHDRAW YOUR CONSENT?

You can withdraw from the survey any time without giving explanations and with no negative consequences: just by letting us know through any communication channel. As well as this, you can exercise your rights under the European General Data Protection Regulation by making a request to Begoña Miñarro begona.minarro@uab.cat, enclosing a photocopy of your ID document. Request for this purpose are available on the website of the UAB Data Protection Office (<https://www.uab.cat/web/about-the-uab/itineraries/data-protection/rights-of-data-subjects-1345828638386.html>)

You may also file a claim before the Catalan Data Protection Authority (<https://apdcat.gencat.cat/ca/contacte/>)

*I hereby:

- Give my consent to the processing of my personal data needed for my participation in the survey that will be carried out by KALEIDOS to identify the capacity building needs and skills of researchers and Research managers to implement open science practices, and to enhance the collaborative work between academic and non-academic societal actors.

About you:

Q1. Type of stakeholder* [for all]

- Academia/Research (including PhD candidates, academic-staff, non-academic staff, and upper-management staff at Universities)
- Civil Society Organisations (independent actors, organised on a not-for-profit and voluntary basis)
- Industry/SMEs
- Public administration/policy-makers

Q2. Name of the University or Research Center* [open-ended] [for stakeholders from Academia]

Q3. Professional profile (a). If you are a Research Manager AND Upper-Management/Senior Staff, please select Upper-Management/senior staff.

Help message: You can take a look at the different researcher profiles here: [Research profiles descriptors | EURAXESS \(europa.eu\)](#) * [for stakeholders from Academia]

- R1 - First Stage Researcher (Up to the point of PhD)
- R2 - Recognised Researcher (PhD holder or equivalent who are not yet fully independent)
- R3 - Established Researcher (Researchers who have developed a level of independence)

- R4 - Leading Researcher (Researchers leading their research area or field)
- Research Manager
- Upper management/senior staff

Q3.1. Main field of science* [for R1-R4 profiles]

Help message: This is the classification of fields of science used by Eurostat:
<https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/eu-semantic-interoperability-catalogue/solution/field-science-and-technology-classification>

- Agricultural sciences
- Engineering and technology
- Humanities
- Medical and health sciences
- Natural sciences
- Social sciences
- Prefer not to answer

Q3.2. Short description of your main tasks* [open-ended] [for Research managers]

Q3.3. Short description of your role* [open-ended] [for upper-management staff]

Q4. Name of your organisation/institution* [open-ended] [for Civil society, Private sector, Public sector representatives]

Q5. Name of the University/Research Center/Organisation that invited you to participate in the survey* [for Civil society, Private sector, Public sector representatives] [open-ended]

Q6. Professional profile (b)* [for Civil society, Private sector, Public sector representatives]

Help message: You can check more details about the European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations (ESCO) classification of occupations here:
https://esco.ec.europa.eu/en/classification/occupation_main

- Armed forces occupations
- Managers
- Professionals
- Technicians and associate professionals
- Clerical support workers
- Skilled agricultural, forestry and fishery workers
- Craft and related trades workers
- Plant and machine operators and assemblers
- Elementary occupations
- Prefer not to answer

Context and definitions [for all]

In December 2023, the European Union approved the European Competence Framework for Researchers 'ResearchComp', based on the new taxonomy of researchers' skills that the European Commission formulated together with stakeholders [for civil society/public sector/private sector/researchers/Research managers]

Source: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/7da29338-37bf-4d51-b5eb-a1571b84c7ad_en?filename=ec_rtd_research-competence-presentation.pdf [for civil society/public sector/private sector/researchers/Research managers]

And since June 2022, the 'CARDEA - Career Acknowledgement for Research (Managers) Delivering for the European Area' EU-funded project is working towards the development a competence-based approach for research manager career development in the European Research Area 'RM Comp', to be adopted at European scale. In April 2024, they published a draft version of it, as it is a living document. [for civil society/public sector/private sector/researchers/Research managers]

Source: <https://www.ucc.ie/en/media/support/hrresearch/RMCompinthenewERAApril2024.pdf> [for civil society/public sector/private sector/researchers/Research managers]

‘ResearchComp’ and ‘RM Comp’ aim to promote the recognition of the researcher and the research manager professions, and to support the development of targeted training and inter-sectoral mobility (in and out of Academia, including Civil Society Organisations, Industry/SMEs and Public administrations). [for civil society/public sector/private sector/researchers/Research managers]

One of the aims of the KALEIDOS project is to create an Open Science profile for researchers and for Research managers, highlighting the skills from ‘ResearchComp’ and ‘RM Comp’ which are related to our definition of Open Science. [for civil society/public sector/private sector/researchers/Research managers]

Open Science, according to UNESCO, builds on open scientific knowledge, open science infrastructures, science communication, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems. [For all]

The KALEIDOS project will work with this holistic vision of Open Science but will concentrate its efforts on the pillars of open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems. The aim is to train researchers and Research managers with the skills needed to extend and explore new approaches of collaboration within academia, but especially with societal actors beyond the scientific community, to better respond to the current challenges and valorise research outputs for the benefit of the whole society [For all]

By now, we have carried out a preliminary selection of skills related to Open Science relevant for researchers and researchers, focusing on three main pillars: systemic vision, collaboration and impact. [for civil society/public sector/private sector/researchers/Research managers]

Before finalising the Open Science Profile for researchers and Research managers, we would like to receive your feedback about the skills selected, as it is very important to consider your experience and point of view as a researcher. Furthermore, it is very useful that you get familiar with the skills that a researcher

develops during their career, so that you can work towards the acquisition of competences that can be recognised inside and outside of Academia [for researchers]

Before finalising the Open Science Profile for researchers and Research managers, we would like to receive your feedback about the skills selected, as it is very important to consider your experience and point of view as a research manager. Furthermore, it is very useful that you get familiar with the skills that a research manager develops during their career, so that you can work towards the acquisition of competences that can be recognised inside and outside of Academia [for Research managers]

Before finalising the Open Science Profile for researchers and Research managers, we would like to receive your feedback about the skills selected, as it is very important to consider your experience and point of view as non-academic actors. Furthermore, it is very useful that you get familiar with the skills that a researcher and a research manager develop during their career, so that they can be acknowledged outside of Academia. [for civil society/public sector/private sector]

Regarding researchers' skills [for civil society/public sector/private sector/researchers/Research managers]

In the Frascati Manual 2015, researchers are defined as “professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, conducting research and improving or developing concepts, theories, models, techniques instrumentation, software or operational methods” (OECD). Furthermore, the Council of the European Union considers that “researchers conduct research, foster innovation, **contribute to solutions to societal challenges and provide policymakers with evidence for informed decision-making processes**”. [for civil society/public sector/private sector]

In this section, we kindly ask you to share your own perspective about the set of competences for researchers related to systemic vision, collaboration, and impact. [for civil society/public sector/private sector/researchers/Research managers]

If you want to consult any competence definition, please go to the ‘ResearchComp’: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/7da29338-37bf-4d51-b5eb-a1571b84c7ad_en?filename=ec_rtd_research-competence-presentation.pdf [for civil society/public sector/private sector/researchers/Research managers]

Q7. Have you collaborated with Universities and have you been in contact with researchers?* [for civil society/public sector/private sector]

- Yes
- No

Even if you have not collaborated with researchers before, we would like to know what you think about the needed skills for them to develop, with the aim of enhancing the impact of potential collaboration between researchers and non-academic actors, like you [for civil society/public sector/private sector, if they answer No to Q7]

Q7.1. The KALEIDOS consortium considers that this set of competences for researchers are related to the systemic vision. Would you leave any of them out? [multiple choice] [for civil society/public sector/private sector/researchers/Research managers]

- Problem solving
- Systemic thinking
- Strategic thinking
- Critical thinking
- Abstract thinking
- Analytical thinking
- No, I think that all of them are related to systemic vision.

Q7.2. Which ones would you add?*[open-ended] [for civil society/public sector/private sector/researchers/Research managers]

Q7.3. Which competences do you think are current strengths of researchers related to system vision?*[multiple choice] [for civil society/public sector/private sector in contact with researchers/researchers/Research managers]

Subtitle: Select maximum 3.

- Problem solving
- Systemic thinking
- Strategic thinking
- Critical thinking
- Abstract thinking
- Analytical thinking

Q7.4. Which competences do you think are current areas of improvement of researchers related to systemic vision?*[multiple choice] [for civil society/public sector/private sector in contact with researchers/researchers/Research managers]

Subtitle: Select maximum 3.

- Problem solving
- Systemic thinking
- Strategic thinking
- Critical thinking
- Abstract thinking
- Analytical thinking

Q8.1. The KALEIDOS consortium considers that this set of competences for researchers are essential to promote collaboration, and wants to include them in the Portfolio of professional skills and competences for Open Science. Would you leave any of them out? [multiple choice] [for civil society/public sector/private sector/researchers/Research managers]

- Develop networks
- Creativity
- Interact professionally
- Negotiate
- Mobilise resources
- Work in teams
- Conduct interdisciplinary research
- Promote inclusion & diversity
- No, I think that all of them are related to collaboration.

Q8.2. Which ones would you add?*[open-ended] [for civil society/public sector/private sector/researchers/Research managers]

Q8.3. Which competences do you think are current strengths of researchers related to collaboration?*[multiple choice] [for civil society/public sector/private sector in contact with researchers/researchers/Research managers]

Subtitle: Select maximum 3.

- Develop networks
- Creativity
- Interact professionally
- Negotiation
- Mobilise resources
- Work in teams
- Conduct interdisciplinary research
- Promote inclusion & diversity

Q8.4. Which competences do you think are current areas of improvement of researchers related to collaboration?*[multiple choice] [for civil society/public sector/private sector in contact with researchers/researchers/Research managers]

Subtitle: Select maximum 3.

- Develop networks
- Creativity
- Interact professionally
- Negotiation
- Mobilise resources
- Work in teams
- Conduct interdisciplinary research
- Promote inclusion & diversity

Q9.1. The KALEIDOS consortium considers that this set of competences for researchers are related to impact. Would you leave any of them out? [multiple choice] [for civil society/public sector/private sector/researchers/Research managers]

- Increase impact of science on policy & society
- Promote the transfer of knowledge
- Communicate to the broad public
- Disseminate results to the research community
- Manage intellectual property rights
- Apply research ethics integrity principles
- Manage research data
- Promote open access publications
- Show entrepreneurial spirit
- Promote open innovation
- Teach in academic or vocational contexts

- Promote citizen science
- No, I think that all of them are related to impact.

Q9.2. Which ones would you add?* [open-ended] [for civil society/public sector/private sector/researchers/Research managers]

Q9.3. Which competences do you think are current strengths of researchers related to impact?* [multiple choice] [for civil society/public sector/private sector in contact with researchers/researchers/Research managers]

Subtitle: Select maximum 3.

- Increase impact of science on policy & society
- Promote the transfer of knowledge
- Communicate to the broad public
- Disseminate results to the research community
- Manage intellectual property rights
- Apply research ethics integrity principles
- Manage research data
- Promote open access publications
- Show entrepreneurial spirit
- Promote open innovation
- Teach in academic or vocational contexts
- Promote citizen science

Q9.4. Which competences do you think are current areas of improvement of researchers related to impact?* [multiple choice] [for civil society/public sector/private sector in contact with researchers/researchers/Research managers]

Subtitle: Select maximum 3.

- Increase impact of science on policy & society
- Promote the transfer of knowledge
- Communicate to the broad public
- Disseminate results to the research community
- Manage intellectual property rights
- Apply research ethics integrity principles
- Manage research data
- Promote open access publications
- Show entrepreneurial spirit
- Promote open innovation
- Teach in academic or vocational contexts
- Promote citizen science

Regarding Research managers' skills:

A research manager, for the KALEIDOS consortium, is someone who contributes to establishing vision and goals, building and implementing research plans and managing the execution of the correspondent activities. Research managers/innovation managers usually have a strong connection between researchers and research leadership, management and operations. [for civil society/private sector/public administration]

In this section, we kindly ask you to share your own perspective about the set of competences for Research managers related to systemic vision, collaboration, and impact. [for civil society/private sector/public administration/researchers/Research managers]

If you want to consult any competence definition, please go to the 'RM Comp': <https://www.ucc.ie/en/media/support/hrresearch/RMCompinthenewERAApril2024.pdf> [for civil society/private sector/public administration/researchers/Research managers]

Q10. Have you ever collaborated with a research manager at a University? [for civil society/private sector/public administration]

- Yes
- No

Even if you have not collaborated with Research managers before, we would like to know what you think about the needed skills for them to develop, with the aim of enhancing the impact of potential collaboration between Research managers and non-academic actors, like you [for civil society/private sector/public administration] [If they answer No to Q10]

Q11.1. The KALEIDOS consortium considers that this set of competences for Research managers are related to systemic vision. Would you leave any of them out? [multiple-choice] [for civil society/public sector/private sector/researchers/Research managers]

- Critical Thinking
- Problem solving
- Cultural Sensibility
- Strategic Planning
- Decision Making
- No, I think that all of them are related to systemic vision.

Q11.2. Which ones would you add?*[open-ended] [for civil society/public sector/private sector/researchers/Research managers]

Q11.3. Which competences do you think are current strengths of Research managers related to systemic vision?*[multiple choice] [for civil society/public sector/private sector in contact with Research managers/researchers/Research managers]

Subtitle: Select maximum 3.

- Critical Thinking
- Problem solving
- Cultural Sensibility
- Strategic Planning
- Decision Making

Q11.4. Which competences do you think are current areas of improvement of Research managers related to systemic vision?*[multiple choice] [for civil society/public sector/private sector in contact with Research managers/researchers/Research managers]

Subtitle: Select maximum 3.

- Critical Thinking
- Problem solving
- Cultural Sensibility
- Strategic Planning
- Decision Making

Q12.1. The KALEIDOS consortium considers that this set of competences for Research managers are related to collaboration. Would you leave any of them out? [multiple-choice] [for civil society/public sector/private sector/researchers/Research managers]

- Building and maintaining relationships with research funders, partners, or other stakeholders
- Managing equality, diversity and inclusion (including gender, disability and racism)
- Creativity
- Professional Flexibility
- Diplomacy, negotiation, and mediation skills
- Handling difficult conversations and partnerships
- Building trust within relevant research and strategic partnerships
- Team Building
- People Management and managing team performance
- Coaching Skills
- Business and commercial liaison management
- No, I think that all of them are related to collaboration.

Q12.2. Which ones would you add?* [open-ended] [for civil society/public sector/private sector/researchers/Research managers]

Q12.3. Which competences do you think are current strengths of Research managers related to collaboration?* [multiple choice] [for civil society/public sector/private sector in contact with Research managers/researchers/Research managers]

Subtitle: Select maximum 3.

- Building and maintaining relationships with research funders, partners, or other stakeholders
- Managing equality, diversity and inclusion (including gender, disability and racism)
- Creativity
- Professional Flexibility
- Diplomacy, negotiation, and mediation skills
- Handling difficult conversations and partnerships
- Building trust within relevant research and strategic partnerships
- Team Building
- People Management and managing team performance
- Coaching Skills
- Business and commercial liaison management

Q12.4. Which competences do you think are current areas of improvement of Research managers related to collaboration?* [multiple choice] [for civil society/public sector/private sector in contact with Research managers/researchers/Research managers]

Subtitle: Select maximum 3.

- Building and maintaining relationships with research funders, partners, or other stakeholders
- Managing equality, diversity and inclusion (including gender, disability and racism)
- Creativity
- Professional Flexibility
- Diplomacy, negotiation, and mediation skills
- Handling difficult conversations and partnerships
- Building trust within relevant research and strategic partnerships
- Team Building
- People Management and managing team performance
- Coaching Skills
- Business and commercial liaison management

Q13.1. The KALEIDOS consortium considers that this set of competences for Research managers are related to impact. Would you leave any of them out? [multiple-choice] [for civil society/public sector/private sector/researchers/Research managers]

- Engagement with key stakeholders
- Designing and implementing research communication plans
- Social media Engagement
- Monitoring and evaluation frameworks and indicators
- Community engagement with research
- Research Outreach
- Technology Transfer
- Academic community relationship collaboration
- Provision of training for outreach engagement
- No, I think that all of them are related to impact.

Q13.2. Which ones would you add?*[open-ended] [for civil society/public sector/private sector/researchers/Research managers]

Q13.3. Which competences do you think are current strengths of Research managers related to impact?*[multiple choice] [for civil society/public sector/private sector in contact with Research managers/researchers/Research managers]

Subtitle: Select maximum 3.

- Engagement with key stakeholders
- Designing and implementing research communication plans
- Social media Engagement
- Monitoring and evaluation frameworks and indicators
- Community engagement with research

- Research Outreach
- Technology Transfer
- Academic community relationship collaboration
- Provision of training for outreach engagement

Q13.4. Which competences do you think are current areas of improvement of Research managers related to impact?* [multiple choice] [for civil society/public sector/private sector in contact with Research managers/researchers/Research managers]

Subtitle: Select maximum 3.

- Engagement with key stakeholders
- Designing and implementing research communication plans
- Social media Engagement
- Monitoring and evaluation frameworks and indicators
- Community engagement with research
- Research Outreach
- Technology Transfer
- Academic community relationship collaboration
- Provision of training for outreach engagement

About open science [for upper-management staff, researchers and Research managers]

Q14. Does your institution have an Open Science policy or strategy?* [for upper-management staff, researchers and Research managers]

- Yes
- No, but the process has started
- No
- I do not know

Q14.1. What does your Open Science strategy include? (general topics).* [open-ended] [for upper-management staff, researchers and Research managers who answered Yes to Q14]

Q15. Does your University have structures or units that are involved in the promotion of Open Science? [for upper-management staff]

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

Q15.1. Which structure(s)/unit(s)?* [open-ended] [for upper-management staff who answered Yes to Q15]

Q16. Does your University have spaces, where Open science practices take place, with the involvement of non-academic actors? [for upper-management staff]

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

Q16.1. Which spaces?* [open-ended] [for upper-management staff]

Q17. How would you rate the maturity level of Open Science knowledge and practices at your University?* [for upper-management staff]

- Very low
- Low
- Intermediate
- Advanced
- Excellent
- Prefer not to answer

Q18. Does your region and/or country have a policy or strategy on Open Science?* [multiple choice] [for upper-management staff]

- Yes, at regional level
- Yes, at national level
- No, but the process has started at regional level
- No, but the process has started at national level
- No
- I do not know

Q18.1. Please provide some details about the Open Science strategies at regional or national level.* [open-ended] [for upper-management staff who answered Yes to Q18]

Help message: You can include a link to a website, if you consider it appropriate.

Q19. Are you aware of any European/international framework(s)/agreements/recommendations on Open Science?. Select all that you are aware of.* [for upper-management staff]

- Open Science and its role in universities: a roadmap for cultural change (LERU, 2018)
- Recommendation on Open Science (UNESCO, 2021)
- CoARA – Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (initiated in 2022)
- Other
- No

Q19.1. Which ones? [open-ended] [for upper-management staff]

Q20. Does your University have specific capacity building activities about open science?* [multiple choice] [for upper-management staff]

- Addressed to PhD Candidates (R1)
- Addressed to recognised researchers (R2)
- Addressed to established researchers (R3)
- Addressed to leading researchers (R4)
- Addressed to Research managers
- Other [open-ended]
- No
- I do not know

Q20.1. Which capacity building activities? Please specify the target(s).* [If they answered yes] [open-ended] [for upper-management staff who answered Yes to Q20]

Q21. Does your University organise other type of activities to foster open science? [for upper-management staff]

- Addressed to PhD Candidates (R1)
- Addressed to recognised researchers (R2)
- Addressed to established researchers (R3)
- Addressed to leading researchers (R4)
- Addressed to Research managers
- Other [open-ended]
- No
- I do not know

Q21.1. Which other type of activities? Please specify the target(s). * [If they answered yes] [open-ended] [for upper-management staff]

Q22. Does your University have an On-boarding program for PhD candidates, academic staff and/or non-academic staff? [for upper-management staff]

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

Q22.1. Does your University include Open Science in the On-boarding program?* [if they answered Yes] [Multiple-choice] [for upper-management staff who answered Yes to Q22]

- Yes, for PhD candidates
- Yes, for the academic staff
- Yes, for the Research managers
- No
- I do not know

Q22.1.1. How is Open Science included in the On-boarding program? Please specify the target(s), * [open-ended] [for upper-management staff who answered Yes to Q22.1]

Q23. Does your University consider (new) metrics for the evaluation of Open Science practices?* [for upper-management staff]

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

Q23.1. Which metrics?* [open-ended] [for upper-management staff who answered Yes to Q23]

Q24. Which changes in Universities would facilitate the collaboration among different actors?* [open-ended] [for civil society/private sector/public sector/researchers/Research managers]

Q25. Which opportunities you see to promote open science?* [open-ended] [for all]

Q26. Which barriers you see to promote open science?* [open-ended] [for all]

About knowledge valorisation [for upper-management staff]

Knowledge valorisation refers to the process of creating social and economic value from knowledge. It involves linking different areas and sectors and transforming data, know-how, and research results into

sustainable products, services, solutions, and knowledge-based policies that benefit society [for upper-management staff]

Q27. Does your University have specific capacity building activities about knowledge valorisation?* [multiple choice] [for upper-management staff]

- Addressed to PhD Candidates (R1)
- Addressed to recognised researchers (R2)
- Addressed to established researchers (R3)
- Addressed to leading researchers (R4)
- Addressed to Research managers
- Other [open-ended]
- No
- I do not know

Q27.1. Which capacity building activities? Please specify the target(s). * [open-ended] [for upper-management staff who answered Yes to Q27]

Q28. Does your University organise other type of activities to foster knowledge valorisation?* [for upper-management staff]

- Addressed to PhD Candidates (R1)
- Addressed to recognised researchers (R2)
- Addressed to established researchers (R3)
- Addressed to leading researchers (R4)
- Addressed to Research managers
- Other [open-ended]
- No

Q28.1. Which other type of activities? Please specify the target(s). * [If they answered yes] [open-ended] [for upper-management staff you answered Yes to Q28]

Q29. Does your University consider (new) metrics for the evaluation of Knowledge Valorisation?* [for upper-management staff]

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

Q29.1. Which metrics? [open-ended] [for upper-management staff who answered Yes to Q29]

Q30. How would you rate the maturity level of Knowledge Valorisation knowledge and practices at your University?* [for upper-management staff]

- Very low
- Low
- Intermediate
- Advanced
- Excellent
- Prefer not to answer

Q31. Are you aware of any European/international framework(s)/agreements/recommendations/code(s) of practice on Knowledge Valorisation?* [Multiple choice] [for upper-management staff]

- Code of practice on the management of intellectual assets for knowledge valorisation
- Code of practice on standardisation in the European Research Area
- Code of practice on citizen-engagement
- Code of practice on industry-academia co-creation for knowledge valorisation
- Other
- No

Q31.1. Which ones? [open-ended] [for upper-management staff who selected Other in Q31]

Personal data: [for all]

Q32. Full name [open-ended]

Q33. Gender*

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary
- Other
- Prefer not to answer

Q34. To which age-range do you belong?*

- Less than 30 years old
- 30-39 years old
- 40-49 years old
- 50-59 years old
- 60 years old or more
- Prefer not to answer

Q35. Country of origin [open-ended]

Q36. What is your education level?*

- High School or Less
- Bachelor's Degree
- Master's Degree
- PhD holder
- Prefer not to answer

Q37. Do you have anything to add?

Annex 2. Demographic data from survey respondents

Type of stakeholder

Figure 30: Professional profile of survey participants from academia

Figure 31: Types of stakeholders from outside of academia as survey participants

Gender

Gender ● Female ● Male ● Non-binary ● Prefer not to answer

Figure 32: Gender of survey participants from academia

Gender ● Female ● Male ● Prefer not to answer

Figure 33: Gender of survey participants from outside academia

Education level

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Figure 34: Education level from survey participants from academia

Figure 35: Education level from survey participants from outside of academia

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